

ANALYZING THE WAY OF SEBASTINIAN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN WRITING FILIPINO WORDS

Paul Racel Mansibang Placer, LPT

Mariano Marcos Memorial High School
Sta. Ana, Manila, Philippines 1009
E-mail: paulracel@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the way of writing the following Filipino word construction: use of apostrophes in omitting phonemes; use of apostrophes in contraction of two words; use of <d> and <r>; use of <nang>, <ng>, and <na'ng>; and use of hyphen. The researcher selected respondents with the use of the cluster sampling technique that has its freedom to select respondents from the group of populations. Teacher-made test is the instrument for this study. Frequency count, mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, and analysis of variance were used to synthesize the results. Based on the results, respondents performed fairly in writing and spelling out Filipino words. Furthermore, problems in orthographic literacy were manifested in item analysis due to the unfamiliarity in the correct spelling of morphemes and its rules. However, when it comes to comparative analysis of data in terms of demographic profile, some group performance in word construction manifested significant differences.

Keywords: word construction, spelling, orthography, demographic profile.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the important skills that should be acquired and enhanced by the students in the classroom is the communicative competence that pertains to the set of required skills for effective communication. It includes the concept of linguistic competence or having the ability to construct and understand meaningful sentences (Geronimo, Petras, & Taylan, 2016). Consequently, according to de Laza, Geronimo, & Taylan (2017), once the language user constructed sentences with grammatical errors, there is a tendency that the message cannot understand by the receiver.

This competence emphasizes acquisition and learning the structure of language based on grammar books and orthographies, and dictionaries, thesaurus, and other references. Due to the dynamism of language based on time and societal situations, the Commission on Filipino Language (Komisyonsa Wikang Filipino or KWF), an agency for language planning and development, release a manual for writing the language called *2013 KWF Ortograpiyang Pambansa* that aims to standardize the graphemes or written symbols, and also aims to feature the reality of progression of language from the era of Abakadang Tagalog to the modernized alphabet in effect to the development of the national language (Almario, 2015).

Written in the history of Filipino language that the language planners were modified the orthographies, from *1987 Alpabeto at Patnubay sa Ispeling*, *2001 Revisyon sa Alfabeto at Patnubay sa Ispeling*, *2009 Gabay sa Ortograpiyang Filipino*, and *2013 KWF Ortograpiyang Pambansa*; and as mentioned, there are existing variety of rules in spelling and writing the language.

However, part of the K-12 Curriculum in Filipino is the teaching and learning of rules in writing the language, and it is expected to demonstrate and apply the knowledge and skills at the senior high school level through technical writing such as research and term papers but based on the experiences of the teacher-researcher for this topic, the students are not well-learned about the proper usage of language, particularly in spelling. This may be supported by Zafra (2016) from his article that the variation in spelling may lessen the national action for codification, standardization, and intellectualization of national language, so that the usage of the language may be accepted, due to the reason that the meaning should be prioritized instead of the spelling itself.

This study aims to determine the way of writing the following word construction of senior high school students from San Sebastian College-Recoletos de Manila: use of apostrophes in omitting phonemes; use of apostrophes in contraction of two words; use of <d> and <r>; use of <nang>, <ng>, and <na'ng>; and use of hyphens. Also, this paper is intended to determine if the demographic profile of respondents may affect the performance in utilizing and writing the Filipino language.

1. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Design

Descriptive design of research is used by the researcher wherein the present situation of phenomenon will describe, list, and interpret through data analysis (Yin, 2003, from Amante, Atienza, and Mendoza, 2008). This aimed to synthesize the data from the respondents of this study.

2.2. Sampling

The researcher selected respondents with the use of the cluster sampling technique that has its freedom to select respondents from the group of populations (Boholano, et al., 2016).

This research was conducted at San Sebastian College-Recoletos de Manila, Senior High School Department. In total, one hundred and one (101) respondents were chosen: twenty-six (26) students from Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM); thirty-five (35) students from General Academic Strand (GAS); and forty (40) students from Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). In terms of sex, fifty-eight (58) students are male, and forty-three (43) students are female.

2.3. Instrumentation

Teacher-made testis the instrument for this study that aims to determine the way of writing the following word construction: use of apostrophes in omitting phonemes; use of apostrophes in contraction of two words; use of <d> and <r>; use of <nang>, <ng>, and <na'ng>; and use of hyphens. It consists of fifty (50) items divided into five (5) parts according to the abovementioned word construction. Each item has three choices based on the common spelling of language users, and the correct answers are based on the rules stated in the *2013 KWF Ortograpiyang Pambansa*. The instrument was validated through item analysis from pilot testing.

2.4. Statistical Treatment

Frequency count, mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, and analysis of variance were used to synthesize the results. Table 1 shows the interpretation of descriptive summary of scores garnered in each area of test:

Table 1: Interpretation of Scores

Interval of Scores	Interpretation
9-10	Very High
7-8	High
5-6	Fair
3-4	Low
0-2	Very Low

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Summary of Scores of Respondents

Table 2: Scores Grouped by Sex

Cate-gory	Omitted Phonemes		Contracted Words		Use of <d> and <r>		Use of <nang>, <ng>, and <na'ng>		Use of Hyphen	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Male	4.69	2.26	5.97	2.06	4.22	1.71	4.74	1.77	5.19	1.89
Female	5.05	2.65	5.77	1.91	5.12	2.05	5.21	2.03	5.63	2.01

Table 2 shows the computed mean and standard deviation of scores from the five parts of the assessment in terms of sex. Based upon estimation, all mean scores of both male and female lie between 5-6 score interval that has the interpretation of "fair." This means that both male and female performed satisfactorily in applying the spelling skills in writing Filipino language. All mean scores have low standard deviation, and it means that the scores are intact.

Table 3: Scores Grouped by Academic Strand

Cate-gory	Omitted Phonemes		Contracted Words		Use of <d> and <r>		Use of <nang>, <ng>, and <na'ng>		Use of Hyphen	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
ABM	5.04	2.73	6.38	1.81	4.50	1.96	4.81	1.94	5.54	1.84
GAS	3.74	2.41	5.20	2.11	4.57	2.36	4.71	1.76	5.20	1.97
STEM	5.68	1.86	6.15	1.87	4.70	1.40	5.23	1.98	5.43	2.02

Table 3 shows the computed mean and standard deviation of scores from the five parts of the assessment in terms of academic strand. All mean scores of all academic strands lie between 5-6 score interval with the interpretation of "fair," except for the mean score of GAS in choosing the correct spelling of words with omitted phonemes that attained the interpretation of "low." Like in the previous table, all mean scores are intact and compressed due to its low standard deviation.

3.2. Summary of Responses based on the Ways of Spelling Out Filipino Words

Table 4: Omitted Phonemes

Statement	without Apostrophe	with Apostrophe	with Phonemic Change; without Apostrophe	No Answer
1. Lakingtuwa ko nangmalamangpupunta kami <u>ro'n</u> ng akingpamilya. <i>I am very happy when I knew we're going to that place with my family.</i>	23 <ron>	70 <ro'n>	5 <run>	3
2. May makikitaro <u>ng</u> palaisdaansa tabi ng bundok. <i>There is fishpond found beside of its mountain.</i>	31 <rong>	60 <ro'ng>	8 <rung>	2
3. Naligo kami noong <u>n</u> ando'nna kami sa falls. <i>We swam after we reached the falls.</i>	30 <nandon>	48 <nando'n>	23 <nandun>	0
4. Bata pa akono <u>n</u> angsinimulan naming libutin ang bansa. <i>I was once a child when we started travelling the country.</i>	25 <non>	62 <no'n>	13 <nun>	1
5. Ang lugarna <u>y</u> on ay palagi konginiisipkapagwalaakongmagawa. <i>I always imagine that place if I have no other things to do.</i>	24 <yon>	60 <'yon>	15 <yun>	2
6. Isa kasi <u>y</u> ongbulkannoongunangpanahon. <i>That was a volcano once upon a time.</i>	12 <yong>	43 <'yong>	45 <yung>	1
7. Madilim <u>n</u> ano'ngnakarating kami sa Albay. <i>It was so dark when we reached Albay.</i>	8 <nong>	34 <no'ng>	58 <nung>	1
8. Kahit <u>g</u> ano'n man aysobrasilangmabaitsamayahin. <i>Even though that is the condition, they are truly kind and joyful.</i>	53 <ganon>	28 <gano'n>	19 <ganun>	1
9. Pagkatapos <u>n</u> 'on, kami ay nagpuntasaPagudpod. <i>After that, we travelled to Pagudpod.</i>	41 <non>	26 <n'on>	32 <nun>	2
10. Pinuntahannamin ang lugar kung <u>s</u> a'npuwedengmakakita ng butanding. <i>We reached the place where we could see whales.</i>	31 <san>	60 <sa'n>	10 <s'an>	0

Table 4 summarizes the responses of students based on ways of spelling out Filipino words with omitted phonemes. According to Almario (2015), apostrophes <'> are used to signify the omitted letter or phoneme in a word or number.

Majority of the respondents chose the correct spelling of the following morphemes: <ro'n> (contracted form of <roon>); <ro'ng> (contracted form of <roong>); <sa'n> (contracted form of <saan>); <no'n> (contracted form of <noon>); and <'yon> (contracted form of <iyon>).

On the other hand, <nando'n> (contracted form of <nandoon>), <'yong> (contracted form of <iyong>), <no'ng> (contracted form of <noong>), <gano'n> (contracted form of <ganoon>), and <n'on> (contracted form of <niyon>) were spelled out by the respondents as <nandon/nandun>, <yun/yon>, <nung/nong>, <ganon/ganun>, and <non/nun>, respectively. This phenomenon was mentioned in Santiago (2003) that the phonemes /u/ and /o/ are interchanging if the syllable contained with the said phonemes have no stress. As observed by the researcher, these are the words utter frequently in basic and casual communication, and the written language is greatly influenced by the spoken language. Texting and chatting can be considered as one of the primary reasons why do Filipino not tend to use apostrophe in writing due to its instantaneous method of delivering messages (Sandoval, 2012).

Table 5: Contracted Words

Statement	without Apostrophe	with Apostrophe	Separated Morphemes; without Apostrophe		No Answer
11. Masiyadongnapalapitsa'yo ang tanawingiyon. <i>That town is close to your heart.</i>	25 <sayo>	75 <sa'yo>	1 <sayo>		0
12. Para sa'kin, ang Coron ay maaaringisamasa 7 Wonders of the World. <i>For me, Coron should belong in the Seven Wonders of the World.</i>	29 <sakin>	68 <sa'kin>	2 <sa kin>		2
13. Ayawtanggapin ng naglibotsa'min ang bayadnamin. <i>The travel guide did not accept our payment.</i>	38 <samin>	61 <sa'min>	0 <sa min>		2
14. Akopala'ngunang-unangnaglambitinsa zip line napagkahaba-haba. <i>I am the first person who took the zipline that is very long.</i>	26 <palang>	44 <pala'ng>	29 <pa lang>		2
15. Bagoumuwi ay nagpasiyakaming mag-roadtripna langmuna. <i>Before we leave, we decided to have a road trip.</i>	46 <nalang>	9 <na'lang>	46 <na lang>		0
16. Bata pa langakonoongpumunta kami saamingprobinsiya. <i>I was once a child when we travelled to our province.</i>	52 <palang>	3 <pala'ng>	45 <pa lang>		1
17. Lubossilangnatuwasabinaybaynilangislasa Visayas. <i>They were so happy in seeing islands in Visayas.</i>	94 <silang>	3 <si'lang>	4 <si lang>		0
18. Sa biyahe, hindipa rinmawawala ang kuwentuhan at paglilitrato. <i>In every travel, telling stories and taking pictures is always present.</i>	16 <parin>		61 <pa rin>	23 <pa din>	1
19. Nagkaroonnarinako ng malalim ng pag-unawasakanila. <i>I deeply understand them.</i>	14 <narin>		60 <narin>	25 <na din>	2
20. Pagka-Santolan, bumabanaako para sumakaynanamansasasakyan. <i>When we were at Santolan, I stepped down from the car to ride another.</i>	40 <nanaman>		55 <nanaman>	2 <nana man>	4

Table 5 shows the summary of responses based on ways of spelling out Filipino words with contracted words. Similar to the previous discussion, usage of apostrophe is still explored; however, this section pertains to the contraction or merging of two words or morphemes. Respondents chose the correct form in writing the following words: <sa'yo> (contracted form of <saiyo>); <sa'kin> (contracted form of <saakin>); and <sa'min> (contracted form of <sa amin>). Also, as expected, almost all of the respondents chose <silang> due to the non-existence of the words <si 'lang> and <si lang>.

Contrary to the result, respondents wrote <pala'ng> (contracted form of <pala ang>) as <palang, pa lang>. The enclitic /pa lang/ has two separate meaning and way of writing: <pa lang> that pertains to the condition of being first or outstanding; and <pala'ng> (contracted form of <pala ang>) that is used to denote the state of surprise in discovering something. Based on the results, the respondents were divided into two in writing the said morpheme.

However, respondents chose the following words correctly: <pa rin>; <narin>; and <nanaman>, instead of <pa din/parin>, <na din/narin>, and <nanaman, nana man>. Above half of the group of the respondents chose <nalang/na 'lang> rather than the correct <na lang>. As mentioned on the previous page, lack of spaces and punctuation marks are caused by the frequent use of technology as a channel of communication.

Table 6: Use of <d> and <r>

Statement	<d>	<r>	either <d> or <r>	No Answer
21. Sira <u>daw</u> ang bangkangmagtatawid sa amin sakabilang isla. <i>The boat that will cross our path to another island was broken.</i>	30 <daw>	42 <raw>	28	1
22. Parang gusto ko naagadtumira <u>doon</u> kasama ang aking ama. <i>Maybe I like to live in that place together with my father.</i>	32 <doon>	49 <roon>	20	0
23. Sa buhay <u>raw</u> , kailangang aliwina ang sarilipaminsan-minsan. <i>In life, we as a person should enjoy ourselves sometimes.</i>	49 <daw>	25 <raw>	27	0
24. Nanguwartar <u>aw</u> sa amin noon iyong agency napinagkatiwalaannamin. <i>According to them, that agency was making money from us.</i>	31 <daw>	60 <raw>	10	0
25. Mahigpit ang patakaran <u>doon</u> sapinuntahannamin. <i>They have strict protocols in that place.</i>	62 <doon>	24 <roon>	15	0
26. Lahat <u>dintayo</u> ay may mga gusto sabuhay. <i>All of us have ambitions in life.</i>	56 <din>	26 <rin>	18	1
27. Gusto kong silang dalhin sakabilang lawa para makitarin <u>nilaiyon</u> . <i>I like to bring them to the other lake to view it.</i>	28 <din>	57 <rin>	15	1
28. Kami <u>rito</u> ay masaya at aktibosapakilalahok samga aktibidades. <i>We are happy and active in taking part in activities.</i>	33 <dito>	55 <rito>	13	0
29. Hindi ko <u>rin</u> lubosakalainnaito ay isasalugarnahindi ko malilimutan. <i>I am not expecting this is the place that I will not forget.</i>	34 <din>	51 <rin>	15	1
30. Namanghaakosamga estrukturang naka-display <u>roon</u> . <i>I am so amazed in that structural displays.</i>	56 <doon>	34 <roon>	11	0

Table 6 projects the summary of responses based on ways of spelling out Filipino words with <d> and <r> at the initial part of morpheme. Respondents were familiar in the rule stated by Almario (2015) that <d> will be converted into <r> when the last phoneme or letter of the morpheme before the adverb (i.e., <din> or <daw> and preposition (i.e., <dito>, <diyan> or <doon>) is a vowel or semivowel (i.e., <y> or <w>). Students used <rin> and <rito> correctly, except for <roon> and <raw>. On the other hand, respondents were not familiar in special rule in this case. The letter will be remained as <d> albeit the last letter is a vowel when the second to the last letter of the morpheme before the said adverb or preposition is <r> (e.g., <sira>, <sara>, <gara>, and the like).

Table 7: Use of <nang>, <ng>, and <na'ng>

Statement	<nang>	<ng>	<na'ng>	No Answer
31. Nagkaroon <u>ng</u> teambuilding ang Tennis Team sa Baguio City. <i>There was team building of Tennis Team at Baguio City.</i>	19	75	7	0
32. Umaganan <u>an</u> nggumising para ilagay ang amingmgagamitsasasakyan. <i>We woke at the morning to pack our belongings inside the car.</i>	62	31	7	1
33. Gabi nan <u>ang</u> kami ay dumating sa terminal ng bus. <i>That was evening when we reached the bus terminal.</i>	61	38	1	1
34. Ang saya ko n <u>ang</u> arawnaiyon. <i>I am very happy in that day.</i>	55	42	4	0
35. Lahat kami ay sabiknasabikn <u>ang</u> magsimba. <i>We were overly excited to attend to church.</i>	52	43	5	1
36. Nilibotnamin ang Baguio n <u>ang</u> masaya. <i>We travelled around Baguio with happiness.</i>	46	51	3	1
37. Nanatili kami sa El Nido n <u>ang</u> tatlongaraw. <i>We stayed at El Nido for three days.</i>	30	68	3	0
38. Kantan <u>ang</u> kanta ang kasama naming tour guide noon saaming van. <i>Our tour guide was singing inside our van.</i>	46	50	5	0
39. Iyon n <u>ang</u> isahasahindi ko malilimutanglugarnanapuntahan ko. <i>That place is one of the unforgettable places for me.</i>	22	24	51	4
40. Wala n <u>ang</u> kinagiliwangtanawin naming magkakaibigan. <i>The place where I always visited together with my friends was gone.</i>	45	34	21	1

Table 7 shows the summary of responses based on ways in using <nang>, <ng>, and <na'ng> contracted words. The <nang> is used according to the following conditions: (1) determiner (synonymous to <noong>); (2) causative conjunction (synonymous to <upang>); (3) contraction of enclitic <na> and noun determiner <ng>; (4) adverb of time; and (5) connector of two repeating verbs. Basically, majority of the respondents chose <ng> correctly as noun determiner.

Also, respondents were aware on the first and third condition, oppositely on the latter conditions. The <na'ng> (contraction form of enclitic <na> and article <ang>) was not familiar by the respondents.

Table 8: Use of Hyphen

Statement	without Hyphen	with Hyphen		Separated Morphemes, without Hyphen	No Answer
41. Baguio ang <u>pinakamagandang</u> lugarnanapuntahan ko. <i>Baguio is the most beautiful place I have ever visited.</i>	68 <pinakamagandang >	14 <pinaka-magandang >		16 <pinakamagandang >	3
42. Tatlongbesespalamangakong <u>nakapag-alok</u> namagbakasyon. <i>I am only invited to have vacation with my friends for three times.</i>	12 <nakapagalok>	61 <nakapag-alok>		28 <nakapagalok>	0
43. Marahil ay <u>marami-ramina</u> akongnapuntahanditosa Filipinas. <i>Maybe, I have reached the various places here in the Philippines.</i>	3 <maramirami>	85 <marami-rami>		13 <marami rami>	0
44. Kung gusto mong <u>magmuni-muni</u> , puwedekangpumuntasa Gateway. <i>If you like to relax, you can visit the Gateway.</i>	18 <magmunimuni>	68 <magmuni-muni>		14 <magmuni muni>	1
45. Sobrangsayanaminsapagkat <u>na-enjoy</u> namin ang summer. <i>We were incredibly happy because we enjoyed the summer.</i>	7 <naenjoy>	53 <na-enjoy>		41 <na enjoy>	1
46. Ang magulang ko ay parehong <u>taga-Bicol</u> . <i>Both of my parents are from Bicol.</i>	5 <tagabicol>	35 <taga-Bicol>		60 <taga Bicol>	1
47. Sa edadna <u>labing-anim</u> nataon, nakapuntanaakosamgasikatnalugar. <i>At the age of sixteen, I have already reached many of the famous places.</i>	9 <labinganim>	65 <labing-anim>		25 <labinganim>	2
58. Naiskongpumuntasa <u>iba'tibang</u> lugarnatin atangkilik ng mga turista. <i>I like to travel in different places that is appreciated by tourists.</i>		34 <iba't-ibang>	8 <ibat-ibang>	59 <iba'tibang>	0
49. Umalis kami noong <u>mag-aalas-singko</u> na ng madaling-araw. <i>We left before 5 o'clock of the morning.</i>		67 <magaalas-singko>	19 <mag-aalas-singko>	15 <mag aalassingko>	0
50. Kailangan naming magligpitdahil hindi kami <u>mag-o-overnight</u> doon. <i>We should pack up things because we will not stay overnight in that place.</i>		51 <mag-oovernight >	30 <mag-o-overnight>	19 <mag oovernight>	1

Table 8 shows the summary of responses based on ways in using hyphen. According to Almario (2015), hyphen <-> is used to separate the following: prefix and root word with vowel at the initial part of morpheme (e.g., <mag-ina>); two repeating root words (e.g., <ano-ano>); prefix and proper noun (e.g., <naka-Gucci>); compound words (e.g., <lipat-bahay>); and prefix and numbers (e.g., <ika-1>, <alasan-dose>).

Respondents correctly chose the following: <nakapag-alok>; <marami-rami>, <magmuni-muni>; <na-enjoy>; and <labing-anim>.

Additionally, respondents chose <pinakamaganda> and <iba'tibang> correctly instead of <pinaka-maganda/pinakamaganda> and <iba't-ibang/ibatibang>, few of the words that always cause confusion. The words <mag-aalas-singko> and <mag-o-overnight> are unusual due to its double hyphen, so that the respondents chose the wrong spelling. Lastly, the <taga-Bicol> that has a prefix and proper noun is also unfamiliar to students.

Comparison of Scores based on Demographic Profile

Table 9: Sex

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper	
A	Equal variances assumed	2.058	.155	.729	99	.468	.35686	.48974	-.61489	1.32860
	Equal variances not assumed			.712	82.175	.478	.35686	.50119	-.64013	1.35385
B	Equal variances assumed	.281	.597	-.492	99	.624	-.19808	.40228	-.99628	.60013
	Equal variances not assumed			-.498	94.050	.620	-.19808	.39783	-.98798	.59182
C	Equal variances assumed	.475	.492	2.383	99	.019	.89214	.37431	.14943	1.63485
	Equal variances not assumed			2.320	80.601	.023	.89214	.38461	.12684	1.65745
D	Equal variances assumed	2.503	.117	1.233	99	.221	.46792	.37959	-.28526	1.22111
	Equal variances not assumed			1.208	83.290	.230	.46792	.38735	-.30245	1.23830
E	Equal variances assumed	.222	.639	1.122	99	.265	.43825	.39059	-.33677	1.21328
	Equal variances not assumed			1.111	87.277	.270	.43825	.39438	-.34558	1.22209

Table 9 projects the result of independent samples test in comparing the scores based on their sexes. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) is used to automatically calculate the t-values and the alpha level that implies the level of significant differences of variables. All variances are equal since each of the calculated values from the Levene’s Test are greater than 0.05. Based on the interpretation, both sexes have the same performance in spelling out words with omitted phonemes (A), contracted words (B), use of <nang>, <ng>, and <na’ng> (D), and use of hyphen (E). Interpretations are based on the following alpha level: .468, .624, .221, and .265, respectively, which are higher than the 5% error or significance level of 0.05.

However, there is a significant difference between sexes in terms of spelling out words with the use of <d> and <r> due to the computed alpha level of 0.19. This possibly means that either male or female knows the basic rules in using words with <d> and <r>at the initial position.

Table 10: Academic Strand

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
A	Between Groups	71.043	2	35.522	6.715	.002
	Within Groups	518.422	98	5.290		
	Total	589.465	100			
B	Between Groups	25.720	2	12.860	3.398	.037
	Within Groups	370.854	98	3.784		
	Total	396.574	100			
C	Between Groups	.687	2	.343	.093	.911
	Within Groups	361.471	98	3.688		
	Total	362.158	100			
D	Between Groups	5.487	2	2.744	.764	.469
	Within Groups	352.156	98	3.593		
	Total	357.644	100			
E	Between Groups	1.866	2	.933	.243	.784
	Within Groups	375.837	98	3.835		
	Total	377.703	100			

Table 10 shows the result of analysis of variance (ANOVA) in comparing the scores based on their academic strands. According to the result, significant differences are manifested in spelling out words with omitted phonemes (A) and contracted words (B), due to its calculated value of .002 and .037, respectively. Guided by the rule of thumb of 0.05 significance level to determine the significant difference of variables, the researcher may suppose that one or two academic strands are using well the apostrophes in spelling out some Filipino words. However, based on the high alpha level of the other three, no significant differences are reflected in writing the language with the use <d> and <r> (C), <nang>, <ng>, and <na’ng> (D), and hyphen (E).

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The respondents performed fairly in choosing and writing the correct spelling of Filipino words.

2. Problems in orthographic literacy were manifested in item analysis due to the unfamiliarity in the correct spelling of morphemes and its rules.

3. When it comes to comparing results in terms of sex, spelling out words with <d> and <r> projected significant difference, the rest has none. However, comparative analysis in terms of academic strand has shown significant difference in spelling out words with omitted phonemes and contracted words.

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